

Towards a common SMP for NFDI

2026 DMP4NFDI SMP-focused Hackathon Report

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Introduction

The steady increase of research software requires a common standard for a metadata schema that makes the software digitally comparable, searchable and findable, and also machine-actionable for automated processing. Software Management Plans (SMPs) are provided as questionnaires facilitating research software to be described with comparable metadata fields. As there are already various SMP questionnaires, it is required to compare them to each other in order to have an umbrella of questions feasible for an overarching questionnaire which is up to date. After an initial comparison of already existing SMPs, a hackathon was conducted for getting feedback from the community of Research Software Engineers (RSEs), both within and beyond the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI).

The hackathon was organised jointly by the Semantic Technologies and Research Data Management teams at ZB MED - Information Centre for Life Sciences in April 2026 within the scope of DMP4NFDI¹, a centralised basic service for managing data management plans (DMPs) and SMPs across NFDI. The event aimed to discuss the importance and relevance of previously identified SMP questions to create a first draft of a NFDI-wide standard for SMP templates. This template is intended to complement the work done around DMPs with the NFDI DMP Template Framework (Schönau et al. 2025) and to help facilitate DMP/SMP interoperability. The hackathon brought together representatives from consortia and institutions involved with software

¹ <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/dmp4nfdi> Last accessed 2026-05-07

development, i.e. DataPLANT, FAIRmat, MaRDI, NFDI4Energy, NFDI4Objects, and Max Planck Information and Technology (MaxIT).

Materials

Various SMPs have been developed over the past 10 years by different organisations and groups with the common goal to gather metadata from research software engineers. Some of the SMPs are more generalised while others focus on more granular and specific aspects, e.g., long-term preservation. Common components of the SMPs are usually gathered around general aspects such as

- software name,
- persistent resource identifiers,
- keywords describing the software, and
- licences.

Furthermore, SMPs usually comprise some information regarding:

- the findability and accessibility of the software available in public repositories or archives;
- documentation about the software, for example for developers and users with regards to technical aspects for executing the software;
- testing, continuous integration, common aspects of quality assurance as well as good practices of software development; and
- software products and the community around the users of the software.

In the following sections, different existing SMP templates are introduced in chronological order that were taken into account for the comparison during the hackathon.

SSI UK

The Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) in the UK published an initial checklist for a SMP in 2016 with its most recent version published in 2018 (Software Sustainability Institute 2018). It provides different categories of overall 55 questions to capture the metadata of research software:

- Type of software: 3 questions
- Users of the Software: 5 questions
- Availability of Software: 8 questions
- Software Support: 6 questions
- Software Contribution to Research: 5 questions
- Software's Relation to Other Research Objects: 6 questions
- Measuring Software Contribution to Research: 5 questions
- Long-term Preservation: 8 questions

ELIXIR SMP

The ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences was created in 2021 as a result of a Hackathon in the BioHackathon series (Alves et al. 2021). The focus of this SMP lays on low-barrier access for people with less technical experience comprising the following categories with 28 questions:

- Accessibility & Licence: 3 questions
- Documentation: 3 questions
- Testing: 2 questions
- Interoperability: 3 questions
- Versioning: 2 questions
- Reproducibility: 11 questions
- Recognition: 4 questions

The type of questions ranges from simple yes/no answers, to complex lists and open questions.

MPDL

The SMP created for the Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL) is represented in the Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO), an open-source tool for creating questionnaires within the scope of Data Management Plans (Anders et al. 2024). Initially drafted in 2022, the questionnaire contains 51 main questions with 8 questions refining a previously asked main question. The questions are categorised in 5 main categories with 20 subcategories as follows:

- General
 - Topic: 4 questions, 1 refined question
 - Software Project Partner(s): 3 questions
 - Software Project Schedule: 2 questions
 - Software Project Management: 3 main questions, 1 refined question
 - Software Development Requirements: 2 questions
- Technical
 - Code: 2 questions
 - Third Party Components and Libraries: 5 questions, 2 refined questions
 - Infrastructure: 3 questions, 1 refined question
 - Preservation: 2 questions
 - Security: 2 questions
- Quality Assurance
 - Governance and Defined Processes: 2 questions, 1 refined question
 - Documentation: 2 questions
 - Testing: 2 questions
- Release and Publish
 - Releasing: 3 questions, 2 refined questions
 - Public Availability: 4 questions
 - Metadata: 2 questions
 - Support: 4 questions

- Legal and Ethics
 - Intellectual Property Rights: 2 questions
 - Licence: 1 question
 - Dual Use: 51 questions

The answers for the questions are open answers, yes/no answers or customizable lists.

eScience

The SMP from the Netherlands eScience Center has been developed according to the guidelines from (Martinez-Ortiz et al. 2023). This SMP comprises 13 questions within two categories, Required Questions and Optional Questions:

- Required Questions: 8 questions
- Optional Questions: 5 questions

The answers to these questions are all free text answers.

DRA Canada

The Digital Research Alliance of Canada published a template for SMPs as a resource for a questionnaire (Zhang and Dhane 2024). It comprises 18 questions in 9 categories:

- Purpose: 1 question
- Documentation and Metadata: 4 questions
- Testing and Deployment Strategy: 1 question
- Version Control & Release Management: 2 questions
- Sharing and Reuse: 4 questions
- Preservation and Long-Term Maintenance: 3 questions
- User Support: 1 question
- Responsibilities and Resources: 2 questions
- Other Concerns: 1 question

All the questions are open to be answered as free text.

DMP OPIDoR

The SMP implemented in the DMP tool DMP OPIDoR leverages machine-actionable metadata with a focus on the FAIR principles (Santangelo et al. 2025). It comprises 31 questions from 5 major categories with 8 subcategories as follows:

- General description of the software
 - Definition and name of the software: 13 questions
- Tools and execution environment
 - Development environment: 7 questions
 - Documentation: 1 question
 - Runtime Environment: 3 questions

- Software Preservation
 - Referencing: 1 question
 - Long-term archiving: 1 question
- Legal issues
 - What are the legal aspects related to this software: 3 questions
- Scientific dissemination
 - Scientific promotion: 2 questions

The answer to these questions ranges from lists to URLs and interactive addition of new elements comprising title, identifier, identifier type, and audience.

ELIXIR-STEERS

This SMP (see report Vergoulis et al. 2025) is implemented using the Software Management Wizard (Alves et al. 2026), and is based upon the ELIXIR SMP guide (Alves et al. 2021). It is one of the outcomes of the project ELIXIR-STEERS (ELIXIR-STEERS partners 2024). The template is called Software Management Planning Knowledge Model (SMP-KM), which is frequently updated and published under the licence Apache 2.0. It allows the creation of custom SMPs according to the provided template with 44 questions in 7 categories as follows:

- General Information: 7 questions
- Collaboration and Licence: 2 questions
- Analysis and Design: 3 questions
- Implementation: 6 questions
- Testing and Quality Assurance: 12 questions
- Versioning and Releases: 5 questions
- Deployment and Delivery: 8 questions

The question type covers open answers, yes/no selection, lists or follow-up questions.

Materials prepared for the hackathon

In order to compare the different SMPs, a spreadsheet was created with tabs for every SMP as well as a summary table comprising an intersection of information between the various SMPs. In every tab for each SMP, the questions are numbered under their categories with columns showing intersections with questions from every other SMPs. Then, the number of intersections are counted in the column “Count”. Furthermore, each question has a column for “In Summary” to indicate whether the question is displayed in the summary table and a column “Summary ID” with the identifier assigned to the matching summary question. An initial comparison was manually conducted before the hackathon for the SMPs “eScience”, “ELIXIR SMP”, “STEERS”, “DRA Canada”, and “MPDL”.

The different SMP sheets, their intersections, and the summary table were discussed with the attendees during the hackathon for further improvement of the initial spreadsheet. In conclusion, it was stated that the comprehensive SMPs from “SSI UK” and “DMP-OPiDOR” are missing and

they are supposed to be added to the comparison. This was conducted by BM after the hackathon before creating the final summary agreed table.

Results

The various SMPs were consolidated from a comparison with each other. Then, a common basis for almost each question was created by its representation in a summary table. Such a common question in the summary table was linked by a unique identifier in the mapping of questions from all the SMPs. Furthermore, the questions in the summary table were grouped into common categories. During the hackathon, these questions and categories were discussed and agreed upon. It was decided which questions would be included in the SMP standard and whether each question would be mandatory or optional. The final agreed amount of questions is the main outcome of the hackathon.

These questions were transferred into a summary table, in which 56 questions were aligned to 6 categories with each question being marked as mandatory or optional:

- Basic information at SMP level: 16 questions, 3 mandatory
- General aspects: 19 questions, 8 mandatory
- Findability and Accessibility: 4 questions, 1 mandatory
- Documentation: 8 questions, 0 mandatory
- Testing, quality assurance, and good practices: 7 questions, 0 mandatory
- Software products and community: 2 questions, 1 mandatory

For each of the questions, further information was provided, if possible:

- Unique identifier
- Comments
- Time of answer (before, during, end of development)
- Cardinality
- Shape (e.g., URL, Date, Free Text, Selection, list, options, checklist)
- Short name
- Rationale
- And mapping questions from the compared SMPs

Final remarks

The summary table will be used as the foundation for a questionnaire integrated into RDMO. For this, the existing NFDI DMP Template will be extended to incorporate the SMP questions in a feasible manner by grouping and creating conditions for follow-up questions. Further tuning of the NFDI DMP/SMP template will then take place in incubator projects within the NFDI framework and dissemination in future events.

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